

Retrospective, Observational Assessment of the Maternal and Fetal Outcomes in Term Pre-Labour Rupture of Membranes

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Aim: The present study was conducted to analyze the maternal and fetal outcome of term Prelabour rupture of membrane in tertiary care hospital in Bihar region.

Methods: This was a retrospective, observational study and it was conducted in the department Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for 1 year. The case records of 240 women admitted as PROM were collected from the medical record department. Out of which, 200 cases of term PROM was included in this study as per the inclusion criteria and the remaining 40 were excluded as per the exclusion criteria.

Results: The age group in this study varies from 18-38 years and the most common age group was 22-25 years (80 cases) 40% followed by 18-21 years 30% and 26-29years 20%. Time of rupture of membrane to the time of delivery varies between 6 hours to more than 24 hours with the maximum of 60% occurred between 12-24 hours followed by 30% occurred later than 24 hours and the least at less than 12 hours (10%). 66% babies had weight >2.5 kgs.

Conclusion: PROM is associated with higher rate of induction and LSCS. Timely intervention will reduce the maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Prelabour rupture of membranes, induction, LSCS, NICU.

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Introduction

Premature rupture of membrane (PROM) [1] refers to the disruption of fetal membranes before the beginning of labor, resulting in spontaneous leakage of amniotic fluid. PROM, which occurs prior to 37 weeks of gestation, defined as preterm PROM as PROM that occurs after 37 weeks gestation defined as term PROM. PROM occurs in approximately 5%–10% of all pregnancies, of which approximately 80% occur at term. [2]

PROM is linked to significant maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality. It has been shown to be the cause of 18%–20% and 21.4% of prenatal mortalities and morbidity respectively. [3,4]

The three causes of fetal death associated with PROM are sepsis, asphyxia, and pulmonary hyperplasia. Women with intrauterine infection deliver earlier than non-infected women, and infants born with sepsis have a mortality rate four times

higher than those without sepsis do. [5] Maternal complications include intra-amniotic infection, which occurs in 13%–60% of women with PROM, placental abruption, and postpartum endometritis. [6,7] Pre-term birth, infection, hypertensive disease, and asphyxia are cited as the most common contributors to maternal and fetal mortality in developing countries (LMICs). [8,9]

Risk factors associated with PROM include low socioeconomic status, low body mass index, tobacco use, PROM or preterm labour in previous pregnancy, infections such as urinary tract infection, sexually transmitted diseases, chorioamnionitis, vaginal bleeding at any time in pregnancy, cervical insufficiency, Polyhydramnios, multiple gestations and invasive procedures like amniocentesis. [10] In addition to above mentioned factors; membrane dysfunction at molecular level, collagen destruction and programmed cell death in fetal membranes also contribute to PROM. Early rupture of membranes may jeopardise the pregnancy contributing to significant maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. Maternal complications associated with PROM are chorioamnionitis, endomyometritis, placental abruption, dysfunctional labour, increased caesarean rate, post-operative wound infection, pelvic abscess, septicaemia and postpartum haemorrhage. [11,12] Perinatal morbidity is due to respiratory distress syndrome, hypothermia, hypoglycaemia, 559 eukomalaci enterocolitis, periventricular 559 eukomalacia, intraventricular haemorrhage, bronchopulmonary dysplasia, meconium aspiration syndrome, neonatal sepsis, umbilical cord prolapse. Three common causes for fetal death associated with PROM are sepsis, asphyxia and pulmonary hyperplasia. Early Onset Neonatal Infection (EONI) is often acquired prenatally in pregnancies with PROM and

is associated with increased neonatal morbidity and mortality. [10]

Early identification of risk factors and management of term PROM are highly warranted to avoid maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality. Hence the present study was conducted to analyze the maternal and fetal outcome of term Prelabour rupture of membrane in tertiary care hospital in Bihar region.

Materials and Methods

This was a retrospective, non-comparative observational study and it was conducted in the department Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for one year. The case records of 240 women admitted as PROM were collected from the medical record department. Out of which, 200 cases of term PROM was included in this study as per the inclusion criteria and the remaining 40 were excluded as per the exclusion criteria. The outcome variables noted for the mother were the age, obstetric score, time of rupture of membranes to time of delivery, colour of liquor and co-morbidities of the mother and for neonates include mode of delivery, birth weight, sex of the baby, APGAR score and NICU admission.

Inclusion criteria

- Singleton pregnancy more than 37 weeks of gestation
- Cervical dilatation less than 3 cm

Exclusion criteria

- Multiple pregnancies
- PPRM
- Patient in active labour

Statistical analysis

The Data were entered in excel spread sheet and checked for correction. The statistical analysis was performed with SPSS version 21.0 software. Descriptive statistics were used for categorical variables and P value of less than 0.05 was taken as statistically significant association

Results

Table 1: Patient characteristics

Variables	N%
Age groups	
18-21	60 (30)
22-25	80 (40)
26-29	40 (20)
30-34	10 (5)
35-38	10 (5)
Time of rupture of membrane to the time of delivery	
<12 hours	20 (10)
12-24 hours	120 (60)
>24 hours	60 (30)
Weight of Baby	
<2.5 kgs	68 (34)
>2.5 kgs	132 (66)
Mode of delivery	
Spontaneous	
Vaginal	46 (23)
LSCS	4 (2)
Induced	
Vaginal	52 (26)
LSCS	98 (49)

The age group in this study varies from 18-38 years and the most common age group was 22-25 years (80 cases) 40% followed by 18-21 years 30% and 26-29 years 20%. Minimum age in this study is 18 years and maximum is 38 years. Time of rupture of membrane to the time of delivery varies between 6 hours to more

than 24 hours with the maximum of 60% occurred between 12-24 hours followed by 30% occurred later than 24 hours and the least at less than 12 hours (10%). 66% babies had weight >2.5 kgs. In this study, 98 mothers (49%) had vaginal deliveries and 102 (451%) delivered via LSCS in both spontaneous and induced labour.

Table 2: Obstetric score

Obstetric score	N%
G1	110 (55)
G2	50 (25)
G3	23 (14)
G4	10 (5)
G5 2 0.8%	2 (1)
G6 1 0.4%	2 (1)

Majority of the patients had G1 obstetric score 55% followed by G2 25%.

Table 3: APGAR score of baby

APGAR score at 5 minutes	N%
5/10	2 (1)
6/10	2 (1)
7/10	16 (8)
8/10	180 (90)

Most of the neonates (90%) had a 5 min APGAR of 8/10

Table 4: Maternal and Neonatal Morbidities

Maternal Morbidities	N%
Wound infection	14 (7)
PPH	4 (2)
Fever	22 (11)
Neonatal Morbidities	
Respiratory distress syndrome	16 (8)
Transient tachypnea of newborn	8 (4)
Meconium aspiration syndrome	4 (2)
low birth weight	2 (1)
Sepsis	2 (1)
Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia	2 (1)
Other causes	6 (3)

Fever, wound infection and PPH were the common maternal morbidity in order of frequency following term PROM. Out of 200 births, 160 (80%) newborns were healthy and 40 (20%) neonates were admitted in Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). The common reasons for NICU admission were respiratory distress syndrome (8%), TTN (4%), meconium aspiration syndrome (2%), low birth weight (1%) and other causes (3%).

Discussion

Prelabour rupture of membrane (PROM), previously known as premature rupture of membranes. PROM refers to the disruption of fetal membranes before the onset of labour resulting in spontaneous leakage of amniotic fluid. [13] It is one of the common problems encountered in day to day obstetric practice and subdivided into term, preterm and mid trimester PROM. PROM that occurs before and after 37 weeks of gestation is defined as preterm and term PROM, respectively. It occurs in approximately 5-10% of all pregnancies, of which about 80% occurs at term. [14]

In this study majority of the cases 105 (42%) belong to 22-25 years, 60 (30%) cases were in the age group of 18-21 years which is similar to the study done by Vlora ademi lbishi et al where 65% of cases were in the age group 20 to 29 years. [11]

Out of the 200 cases, majority of them required Induction followed by

acceleration and the remaining went in for spontaneous labour which is similar to the study done by Amulya MN et al and Hexia Xia et al. [15,16] Statistically no difference in the mode of delivery i.e 49% delivered vaginally and 51% delivered by LSCS, according to our study. The common indications for LSCS were oligohydramnios and fetal distress. The other indications for LSCS include failed induction, non-progressive labour and previous LSCS. The higher incidence of LSCS was related to the high rates of induction and maternal comorbidities. The commonly associated maternal comorbidities were Pregnancy Induced Hypertension, Rhesus Negative and anemia in order of frequency. Duration of PROM and latency were significantly associated with unfavourable maternal and fetal outcome. In less than 12 hours from time of rupture of membranes, 10% of mothers delivered, within 12 hours - 24 hours 60% delivered and 30% delivered after 24 hours.

Post-operative wound infection was present in 7% of patients leading to prolonged stay in the hospital which is higher than the study done by Sailaja et al which showed only 2.5% of post-operative wound infection. [17] The fetal outcome in this study includes 34% of low birth weight; this may be associated with maternal co-morbidities such as PIH, anemia and BOH. Most of the neonates

(90%) had a 5 min APGAR of 8/10. The neonatal mortality in this study was 0.4% which is comparatively lower than the previous study done by Shruti Gupta et al that showed 2% neonatal mortality [18] and Arpita. A et al that showed perinatal mortality rate of 1.43%. [19,20]

Conclusion

The term Prelabour rupture of membranes remains as one of the challenging situation to be tackled by practicing obstetricians and an important cause for maternal and fetal morbidity with increased rate of caesarean section delivery. LSCS increases the long term morbidity for the mother and increased hospital costs. Majority of the term PROM, occurs in primigravida between 18 to 25years of age. Apart from early diagnosis and prompt management of term PROM, it is highly essential to educate the antenatal mother regarding regular and timely antenatal checkup for the better maternal and fetal outcome.

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